

Polarographic investigation of the catalytical adsorptive complex behavior of trace iron

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In HAc-NaAc (1 : 1) buffer solution, Fe^{III}-5-Br-PADAP-NO₃ system sensitively presents a reductive wave at a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE). The reductive wave is a catalytical adsorptive complex wave. In 0.05 mol dm⁻³ HAc-NaAc and 4.0 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ 5-Br-PADAP solution, the second derivative peak height of the reductive wave is linearly proportional to the concentration of Fe^{III} in the range from 1.0 × 10⁻¹⁰ to 1.0 × 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³. The detection limit is 6.0 × 10⁻¹¹ mol dm⁻³. The method has been applied to determine trace amount of iron samples of pig meat and tap water.

Adsorptive stripping voltammetry is a useful method to detect electroactive species that cannot be accumulated by electrolysis¹. Few ligands have been suggested for the determination of iron based on the adsorptive accumulation at a static mercury drop electrode. The adsorption voltammetry of complex formed by iron and catechol at a HMDE has been reported; the detection limit² is 6.0 × 10⁻¹⁰ mol dm⁻³. But the method has limitations such as a narrow linear range and being interfered by copper and lead. Another new sensitive adsorptive voltammetric procedure based on the adsorption of the chelate of iron with solochrome violet RS on the surface of a HMDE has been described³, while the linearity in the range of one order (3.6 × 10⁻⁸–3.6 × 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³) by controlling the pre-concentration time is inconvenient for routine analysis.

In HAc-NaAc medium, the Fe^{III}-5-Br-PADAP complex can be strongly adsorbed on the HMDE and presents a reductive peak whose peak potential is -0.50 V. After the addition of HNO₃, a catalytical circulation is set up and the peak current increases. The detection limit is 6.0 × 10⁻¹¹ mol dm⁻³. This method was used to determine trace iron in meat and tap water samples, and satisfactory results were obtained. The polarographic wave was found to have dual characteristics of adsorption wave and dynamic wave.

Results and Discussion

Optimum conditions : The effects of pH value and the concentration of 5-Br-PADAP on the peak current show the best pH value at 4.5, and the best concentration of 5-Br-PADAP at 4.0 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³.

When oxidative reagents such as KClO₄, H₂O₂, HNO₃, NH₂OH-HCl were added, the reductive peak current increased under all conditions. But the influence of HNO₃

was the greatest. The peak current increased with the increase of the concentration of HNO₃. When the concentration of HNO₃ was larger than 0.01 mol dm⁻³, the peak current increase became slow, so 0.01 mol dm⁻³ was chosen as the best concentration of HNO₃.

The peak current increased with the *E*_a shifted in the negative direction from -0.10 to -0.3 V. When *E*_a reached -0.35 V, the peak shape worsened, so -0.30 V was chosen.

Voltammetric characteristic and electrode procedure of the complex : Within certain time, the peak current of the complex increased with the increase in preconcentration time. From electrocapillary curve it appears that the surface tension of Hg decreases on the addition of Fe^{III} and 5-Br-PADAP. These characteristics indicate that the reductive peak is adsorptive one⁴.

Temperature coefficients (*α*) of the peak current in the temperature range are as follows : 10–20°, 6%; 20–25°, 4%; 25–30°, -0.5%; 30–35°, -3.6%/°C. The temperature coefficient decreases with the increase of temperature and finally a negative value is obtained, which is typical of a preliminary reaction of the adsorbed reactants on the electrode.

When surfactants such as CTMAB, CPB and PVA were added, the peak current decreased obviously. The experimental results show that there is no linear relationship between the peak current and the square-root of the scan rate. The polarographic wave of the complex is an adsorptive wave⁵.

The cyclic voltammogram of the Fe^{III}-5-Br-PADAP-NO₃ system is shown in Fig. 2. There is only a reductive wave and not oxidative wave, which demonstrates that the electrode process is a totally irreversible reductive process.

From the above results, the electrode process may be

Fig. 1. Second derivative voltammogram of Fe^{III}-5-Br-PADAP-NO₃ system : (a) 0.05 mol dm⁻³ HAC-NaAc + 4.0 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ 5-Br-PADAP + 0.01 mol dm⁻³ HNO₃ and (b) a + 5.0 × 10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻³ Fe^{III}; E_a = -0.3 V, t_a = 60 s, V = 100 mV s⁻¹.

considered to be as follows : Fe^{III}-5-Br-PADAP complex adsorbed on the surface of the electrode; Fe^{III} reduced to Fe^{II}. The parallel chemical reaction was that Fe^{II} was oxidated to Fe^{III} by NO₃⁻.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram : (a) 0.05 mol dm⁻³ HAC-NaAc + 4.0 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ 5-Br-PADAP + 0.01 mol dm⁻³ HNO₃ and (b) a + 1.0 × 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³ Fe^{III}.

The large catalytical current was thus generated by such circular reaction :

Analytical application :

Under the optimum experimental conditions, the reduc-

tive peak current is linearly proportional to the concentration of Fe^{III} in the range from 1.0 × 10⁻⁶ to 1.0 × 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³. The detection limit is 6.0 × 10⁻¹¹ mol dm⁻³.

A 1000-fold excess of Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mn^{II}; 500-fold excess of Al^{III}, Na^I, K^I, W^{IV}, Mo^{IV}; 200-fold excess of Sn^{IV}, Ti^{IV}, Co^{II}, N^{III}; 100-fold excess of Zn^{II}, Pb^{II} did not interfere with the determination of 5.0 × 10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻³ Fe^{III}.

The results of sample analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of samples analyzed

Sample	Lean pig meat	Fat pig meat	Water-1	Water-2
Fe ^{III} content (μg g ⁻¹)	17.0	9.7	0.013	0.024
Deviation coefficient (%)	2.44	3.30	3.10	2.96
Recovery (%)	95	96	98.6	96.8

Experimental

A voltammetric analyzer (Model 79-1: Jinan Electronic Instrument, China) coupled with a X-Y recorder (Model 3086-11: Shanghai Dahua Instrument, China) was used in connection with a self-made detection cell. The three-electrode system consisted of a HMDE as a working electrode, a Pt plate as a counter electrode and a SCE as a reference electrode. Potential was measured against the SCE. The pH values were measured with a pH meter (Model pHs-2: Shanghai Second Analytical Instrument, China).

A stock solution (1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³) of Fe^{III} was prepared by dissolving iron metal (G.R.) in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ HCl (G.R.), and standard solutions were obtained by diluting the stock solution with triple-distilled water. A 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ stock solution of 5-Br-PADAP (A.R.) was prepared in ethanol (G.R.) and diluted solutions were prepared by serial dilution with water. Solutions of 1.0 mol dm⁻³ HAC-NaAc (1 : 1) and 0.3 mol dm⁻³ HNO₃ were prepared.

Triple-distilled water was used throughout.

Procedure : A mixture of 1.0 mol dm⁻³ HAC-NaAc solution (1.5 ml), 1.0 × 10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻³ 5-Br-PADAP solution (120 μl), 0.3 mol dm⁻³ HNO₃ solution (1 ml) and certain amount of iron solution was diluted to 30 ml with water and deaerated for about 10 min. Measurements were carried out after a preconcentration step in which the solution was stirred for 60 s and a preconcentration potential E_a of -0.30 V (vs SCE) was applied. After a rest period of 20 s, the second derivative voltammetric curve (Fig. 1) from -0.30 to -0.8 V with a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹ was recorded.

Sample analysis : Meat sample (5 g) was digested with $\text{HClO}_4\text{-HNO}_3$ (1 : 5 v/v; 30 ml) and the resulting deposit was dissolved in deionised water and iron content determined by standard addition method as above.

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